

The Homogeneous First-Order Roots of the Klein–Gordon Operator

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Abstract

We classify first-order factorisations of the Klein–Gordon operator acting on real multivector fields. The factorisation problem requires a field space closed under left Clifford-vector differentiation and right Clifford multiplication, which fixes the natural intrinsic setting as the real spacetime algebra $\text{Cl}(1, 3)$.

Within the two-sided ansatz

$$\nabla\Psi = -M\Psi K, \quad K^2 = -1,$$

the requirement that the square reproduce the scalar Klein–Gordon operator for arbitrary multivector fields forces M to be either a real scalar μ or a real scalar multiple μI of the pseudoscalar. With K further restricted to a single definite Clifford grade, four primitive branches arise for the scalar-mass case $M = \mu$: a spacelike vector, a timelike trivector, a spacelike bivector, and the pseudoscalar. The pseudoscalar-left case $M = \mu I$ is shown to permute these same branches rather than producing new ones. After choosing a timelike unit vector, the even and odd parts of the multivector field form a natural Clifford doublet,

$$\Psi = \psi_1 + \psi_2\gamma_0, \quad \psi_{1,2} \in \text{Cl}^+(1, 3).$$

The timelike trivector and spacelike bivector branches reduce to Dirac equations for even Clifford spinors, though in different bases of the doublet. In both cases the propagation is governed by a fixed right-acting spacelike bivector B satisfying $B^2 = -1$, giving the usual Dirac complex structure geometrically inside the real spacetime algebra. The spacelike vector branch is also algebraically consistent and admits Klein–Gordon mass-shell oscillatory modes, but its effective imaginary structure is momentum-dependent and two-sided rather than a universal fixed right-acting bivector. The pseudoscalar branch reduces, after internal recombination, to the same vector-root type.

The grade-defined Clifford classification thereby separates the Dirac-type first-order propagation structure from additional structurally admissible massive first-order root structures that are not governed by a universal Dirac spin-plane phase. Within the Dirac-type branches, the Dirac equation, its geometric complex phase, and a natural two-dimensional internal doublet structure emerge directly from the first-order roots already contained in the Klein–Gordon operator.

Introduction

Dirac’s construction of a first-order square root of the Klein–Gordon operator [1, 2] is one of the foundations of modern relativistic quantum theory. By linearising the scalar relativistic wave equation, Dirac introduced spin, predicted antimatter, and established the framework for first-order relativistic wave equations. In the conventional complex matrix-spinor formalism, the Dirac equation is usually treated as the distinguished first-order, Lorentz-covariant square root of the Klein–Gordon operator for an irreducible spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ complex spinor with a fixed scalar imaginary unit; see, for example, Weinberg [3] and Peskin–Schroeder [4].

That standard formulation is already adapted to a one-sided complex module representation. Clifford generators act from the left as matrices, while the complex structure is supplied externally by the scalar imaginary unit i . Right multiplication by independent Clifford elements is not available as an intrinsic operation on the spinor coefficients. Thus the usual formulation gives a powerful representation of the Dirac sector, but not a classification of all homogeneous right-multiplied Clifford roots.

When the field is allowed to take values in the full spacetime algebra $\text{Cl}(1, 3)$, the Clifford root problem can be formulated intrinsically. The factorisation of the d’Alembert operator already introduces Clifford generators acting from the left. The corresponding first-order root problem may also involve right multiplication by a homogeneous Clifford element K , giving the ansatz

$$\nabla\Psi = -\mu\Psi K, \quad K^2 = -1.$$

Here the right root K is not known in advance. It is the object to be classified. Replacing the right action at the outset by a fixed scalar imaginary unit, or by a preselected right-acting bivector, would therefore restrict the problem before the classification has been carried out.

The full root problem consequently requires a field space on which both left Clifford differentiation and homogeneous right Clifford multiplication are internal operations. This makes the real spacetime algebra itself the natural intrinsic domain:

$$\Psi(x) \in \text{Cl}(1, 3).$$

A one-sided complex spinor module may then be recovered as a reduced description after a Dirac-type right-acting complex structure has been selected.

Once a timelike unit vector γ_0 has been chosen, the odd part of Ψ may be written as an even element multiplied by γ_0 . Thus the Lorentz-invariant even–odd grading of the full multivector field may be represented as the Clifford doublet

$$\Psi = \psi_1 + \psi_2\gamma_0, \quad \psi_{1,2} \in \text{Cl}^+(1, 3).$$

The doublet is therefore not an externally postulated internal space. It is the invariant even–odd structure of a single real multivector field, written in a spacetime-split form. Changing the timelike vector changes the representative doublet basis, but not the underlying even–odd decomposition.

The present paper classifies the primitive homogeneous first-order roots of the Klein–Gordon operator in $\text{Cl}(1,3)$. By a primitive homogeneous root we mean a constant right multiplier K of definite Clifford grade satisfying

$$K^2 = -1.$$

The condition is then satisfied within one Lorentz-geometric grade type, rather than through cancellations between different grades. Mixed-grade right multipliers may also satisfy $K^2 = -1$ under additional algebraic constraints, but such roots combine homogeneous mechanisms rather than defining new primitive grade-defined branches. The present classification is therefore a classification of Lorentz-geometric grade-pure mechanisms, not of the full algebraic variety of all constant $K \in \text{Cl}(1,3)$ satisfying $K^2 = -1$.

Within the scalar-mass ansatz

$$\nabla\Psi = -\mu\Psi K, \quad K^2 = -1,$$

the primitive homogeneous branches are: a spacelike vector, a timelike trivector, a spacelike bivector, and the pseudoscalar. The corresponding pseudoscalar-left mass ansatz is treated separately in the appendix and is shown to permute these same branches rather than producing new homogeneous root structures.

The four branches have different Clifford-geometric content. In what follows, we call a branch Dirac-type if, after possible doublet diagonalisation, its first-order equations for even Clifford spinors are governed by a fixed right-acting even spacelike bivector B with $B^2 = -1$. Branches lacking such a universal fixed right-acting bivector phase will be called vector-root-type.

The timelike trivector and spacelike bivector branches are Dirac-type branches. They reduce to ordinary Dirac equations for even Clifford spinors, though in different bases of the doublet. In both cases the relevant phase generator is a fixed right-acting spacelike bivector B satisfying $B^2 = -1$, which supplies the usual Dirac complex structure geometrically inside the real spacetime algebra.

The spacelike vector branch is algebraically consistent and admits massive Klein–Gordon mass-shell oscillatory modes, but its oscillatory structure is not generated by a fixed right-acting even bivector. For a mass-shell mode with four-momentum p , its effective imaginary structure is a two-sided operation depending on p and on the spacelike vector root. It defines a real complex structure on the finite-dimensional amplitude space associated with a fixed mass-shell momentum, but not a universal internal complex structure on the full field space. The pseudoscalar branch reduces, after an internal recombination of the doublet components, to this same vector-root type.

Thus the homogeneous classification contains two Dirac-type branches and two non-Dirac vector-root-type branches. The Dirac complex structure is selected geometrically within the Dirac-type branches as a spacelike bivector squaring to -1 , realised in a canonical adapted frame as $B = I\sigma_3$. In this sense the Dirac equation, its associated complex phase, and

a natural internal doublet structure arise directly from the Dirac-type homogeneous roots already contained in the Klein–Gordon operator, while the full Clifford classification also exposes additional massive first-order root structures not governed by a universal Dirac spin-plane phase.

For background on the spacetime algebra formalism see [5, 6] and Lounesto [7].

Geometric Setting and First-Order Ansatz

We work in the spacetime algebra $\text{Cl}(1, 3)$ with signature $(+, -, -, -)$ and basis vectors γ_μ . Once a timelike unit vector γ_0 has been chosen, we define the relative Pauli elements

$$\sigma_k := \gamma_k \gamma_0.$$

In particular,

$$\sigma_3 = \gamma_3 \gamma_0, \quad \gamma_0 \sigma_3 = \gamma_0 \gamma_3 \gamma_0 = -\gamma_3.$$

The choice of γ_0 fixes a spacetime split and hence a decomposition of the full algebra into even elements and their γ_0 -shifted odd partners.

The canonical representatives used below are adapted representatives of Lorentz orbits of root elements, not additional background structures. Under a Lorentz transformation, the field, the chosen timelike vector, and the root element transform together. Thus expressions such as $B = I\sigma_3$, $K = \gamma_0 B$, or $s = \gamma_3$ are convenient representatives used to display the algebra in an adapted frame. The classification is therefore Lorentz-covariant: individual root representatives select directions or planes, but the branch structure is defined by their Lorentz-geometric orbit type.

The Klein–Gordon equation is

$$(\square + m^2)\Psi = 0, \quad \square = \nabla \cdot \nabla, \quad \nabla = \gamma^\mu \partial_\mu. \quad (1)$$

A first-order factorisation of the d'Alembert operator introduces Clifford generators through

$$\gamma^\mu \gamma^\nu + \gamma^\nu \gamma^\mu = 2\eta^{\mu\nu}.$$

Thus the differential part of the root acts naturally by left multiplication with Clifford vectors.

The first-order root problem considered here also allows an algebraic right multiplier K . Since K is part of the structure to be classified, its grade and geometric type cannot be fixed in advance. The field space must therefore be closed under both left Clifford-vector differentiation and right Clifford multiplication. This forces the intrinsic domain of the homogeneous root problem to be the real spacetime algebra:

$$\Psi(x) \in \text{Cl}(1, 3).$$

Thus Ψ is a real multivector field with sixteen real components, and the Klein–Gordon equation is understood componentwise.

With respect to the chosen timelike vector γ_0 , the full multivector field decomposes as the Clifford doublet

$$\Psi = \psi_1 + \psi_2 \gamma_0, \quad \psi_{1,2} \in \text{Cl}^+(1, 3). \quad (2)$$

This is a spacetime-split representation of the even and odd parts of Ψ , not an additional postulate of a separate internal doublet space. The doublet structure is inherited from the full multivector field once the right action of γ_0 is used to express odd elements as even elements multiplied by γ_0 .

In branches involving a spacelike bivector root B , the timelike vector γ_0 may be chosen orthogonal to the spacelike two-plane of B , so that in the adapted representative

$$[B, \gamma_0] = 0.$$

Similarly, for a spacelike vector root s , the adapted choice has γ_0 orthogonal to s , giving

$$\gamma_0 s = -s \gamma_0.$$

These are choices of representative within Lorentz orbits, not additional restrictions on the branches.

The even components $\psi_{1,2}$ are even Clifford spinor fields. In the Dirac-type branches they become ordinary spacetime-algebra Dirac spinors. A non-null even spinor admits the polar decomposition

$$\psi = \sqrt{\rho} e^{I\beta/2} R, \quad R\tilde{R} = 1, \quad \rho > 0, \quad (3)$$

where ρ and β are scalars and R is a Lorentz rotor.

Dirac-type roots. In this paper we call a homogeneous root Dirac-type if, after possible doublet diagonalisation, the resulting even-spinor equations are governed by a fixed right-acting even spacelike bivector B , with $B^2 = -1$. Roots lacking such a momentum-independent right-acting bivector phase will be called vector-root-type.

We classify homogeneous Clifford roots of the form

$$\nabla\Psi = -M\Psi K, \quad (4)$$

where M and K are constant Clifford elements of definite grade. Throughout, “homogeneous” means definite-grade in the primitive sense: the relevant square condition is satisfied within one Lorentz-geometric grade type rather than through cancellations between different grades.

Allowed homogeneous left multipliers in the present ansatz. Within the present homogeneous Lorentz-covariant ansatz, the second application of ∇ is required to reduce directly to the scalar Klein–Gordon operator for arbitrary multivector fields. This imposes a strong restriction on the possible homogeneous left mass multipliers.

Lemma. Let M be a constant homogeneous Clifford element in the first-order ansatz

$$\nabla\Psi = -M\Psi K,$$

with constant right multiplier K . If this equation is to square directly to a scalar Klein–Gordon equation for arbitrary multivector fields Ψ , then M must have a universal commutation parity with all vectors. Hence, within $\text{Cl}(1, 3)$, the only homogeneous left multipliers with this universal vector-commutation property are

$$M = \mu \quad \text{or} \quad M = \mu I,$$

with μ a real scalar.

Proof. Acting once more with ∇ from the left gives

$$\nabla^2\Psi = -\gamma^\mu M \partial_\mu\Psi K.$$

At a point, the first derivatives $\partial_\mu\Psi$ of an arbitrary multivector field are algebraically independent as elements of $\text{Cl}(1,3)$: no nonzero linear combination of the $\partial_\mu\Psi$ with constant Clifford coefficients vanishes for all choices of field Ψ . Therefore, for the right-hand side to be expressible uniformly as a scalar multiple of $-M(\nabla\Psi)K$, it is necessary that

$$\gamma^\mu M = \varepsilon M \gamma^\mu$$

hold with the *same* sign $\varepsilon = \pm 1$ for all μ . If different basis vectors gave different signs, the expression $-\sum_\mu \gamma^\mu M \partial_\mu\Psi K$ could not be written as a single scalar multiple of $-M \sum_\mu \gamma^\mu \partial_\mu\Psi K$ for arbitrary Ψ .

When this universal commutation parity holds,

$$\nabla^2\Psi = -\varepsilon M(\nabla\Psi)K = \varepsilon M^2\Psi K^2.$$

For this to reproduce the scalar Klein–Gordon equation for arbitrary Ψ , the product $\varepsilon M^2 K^2$ must be a negative scalar, with

$$\varepsilon M^2 K^2 = -m^2.$$

It remains to identify the homogeneous elements $M \in \text{Cl}(1,3)$ with universal commutation parity with all vectors. If M commutes with all vectors, then M lies in the center of $\text{Cl}(1,3)$. Since the algebra has even dimension, this center is \mathbb{R} , so M is scalar. If M anticommutes with all vectors, then MI^{-1} commutes with all vectors, because the pseudoscalar I itself anticommutes with all vectors in $\text{Cl}(1,3)$. Therefore MI^{-1} is scalar, and M is a scalar multiple of I . Thus the only homogeneous left multipliers of this type are

$$M = \mu \quad \text{and} \quad M = \mu I,$$

with μ a real scalar. \square

This restriction does not exclude more general matrix-valued, projector-valued, or multi-component first-order systems whose square is the Klein–Gordon operator. It excludes them from the present homogeneous Clifford ansatz with a single constant left multiplier and with the second-order equation required to reduce directly to the scalar Klein–Gordon equation for arbitrary multivector fields.

Mixed scalar-pseudoscalar choices such as $M = a + bI$ are not included in the primitive homogeneous classification of the present paper. They combine the two homogeneous left multipliers and would require a separate mixed-grade analysis.

In the main text we treat the scalar-mass case $M = \mu$. The pseudoscalar-left alternative $M = \mu I$ is analysed in Appendix A. As shown there, because I commutes with the even fields $\psi_{1,2}$ but anticommutes with the γ_0 in the doublet decomposition, the pseudoscalar-left cases reduce to the same scalar-mass branches analysed below and introduce no new independent homogeneous root structure.

For $M = \mu$, the first-order root equation is

$$\nabla\Psi = -\mu\Psi K. \quad (5)$$

Acting again with ∇ from the left gives

$$\nabla^2\Psi = -\mu(\nabla\Psi)K.$$

Using (5), we obtain

$$\nabla^2\Psi = \mu^2\Psi K^2.$$

Matching this with the Klein–Gordon equation (1) yields

$$\mu = \pm m, \quad K^2 = -1. \quad (6)$$

The sign of μ may equivalently be absorbed into $K \mapsto -K$; we retain $\mu = \pm m$ to display the usual mass-sign convention. Thus every scalar-mass root of the present homogeneous type takes the form

$$\nabla\Psi = -\mu\Psi K, \quad K^2 = -1. \quad (7)$$

Classification of the Root Branches

We classify homogeneous Clifford roots of the form

$$\nabla\Psi = -M\Psi K, \quad (8)$$

where M and K are constant Clifford elements of definite grade. Throughout, “homogeneous” means definite-grade in the primitive sense: the relevant square condition is satisfied by one grade-pure geometric type, such as a spacelike vector, a spacelike bivector, a timelike trivector, or the pseudoscalar, rather than through cancellations between different grades.

For vectors, trivectors, and the pseudoscalar, the homogeneous representatives are already blades. The only slightly more delicate case is a bivector B . For a bivector in four dimensions,

$$B^2 = B \cdot B + B \wedge B.$$

Thus the condition $B^2 = -1$ requires

$$B \wedge B = 0, \quad B \cdot B = -1.$$

In four dimensions $B \wedge B = 0$ is precisely the simplicity condition, equivalent to $B = a \wedge b$ for some vectors a and b . Hence B is a simple spacelike bivector, and the homogeneous roots are in all four cases represented by blades.¹

¹For the product of two bivectors A and B , grades 0, 2, 4 may occur:

$$AB = \langle AB \rangle_0 + \langle AB \rangle_2 + \langle AB \rangle_4.$$

The grade-2 part is the commutator product $A \times B = \frac{1}{2}(AB - BA)$. In the square of a single bivector this contribution is $B \times B = \frac{1}{2}(BB - BB) = 0$. Thus B^2 contains only scalar and grade-four parts, giving $B^2 = B \cdot B + B \wedge B$.

The four primitive branches may be summarised as follows:

Root K	Grade	Doublet behaviour	Sector
$s, s^2 = -1$	1	diagonal	vector-root type
$\gamma_0 B, B^2 = -1$	3	diagonal	Dirac-type
$B, B^2 = -1$	2	off-diagonal	Dirac-type
I	4	off-diagonal	vector-root type

Here s is a spacelike unit vector, B is a simple spacelike bivector, and $\gamma_0 B$ represents a timelike trivector in an adapted frame.

Odd grade. If K is odd, the even and odd parts of $\Psi = \psi_1 + \psi_2 \gamma_0$ decouple, so ψ_1 and ψ_2 satisfy separate first-order equations. The odd homogeneous blades in $\text{Cl}(1, 3)$ with $K^2 = -1$ are:

- (i) spacelike vectors, (ii) timelike trivectors.

By a timelike trivector we mean a simple three-blade whose associated three-plane contains one timelike and two spacelike directions. Equivalently, its dual is spacelike. Such a trivector is Lorentz-equivalent to

$$K = \gamma_0 B,$$

where B is a simple spacelike bivector with $B^2 = -1$ and $[B, \gamma_0] = 0$ in the adapted frame.

Even grade. If K is even, the equation couples the two entries of the doublet. The even homogeneous blades in $\text{Cl}(1, 3)$ with $K^2 = -1$ are:

- (i) spacelike bivectors, (ii) the pseudoscalar I .

These four cases exhaust the primitive homogeneous Lorentz-geometric root branches of the Clifford ansatz. The odd branches decouple the doublet components, whereas the even branches couple them. The branches differ not in algebraic consistency, but in the Clifford-geometric structure of their solutions. The trivector and bivector branches are Dirac-type, governed by a fixed right-acting even spacelike bivector B with $B^2 = -1$. The vector and pseudoscalar branches form a distinct non-Dirac vector-root sector.

The Vector Branch

For the vector branch we choose the adapted representative

$$K = s, \quad s^2 = -1, \quad \gamma_0 s = -s \gamma_0,$$

where s is a spacelike unit vector and γ_0 is orthogonal to s . The root equation becomes

$$\nabla \Psi = -\mu \Psi s, \quad s^2 = -1. \tag{9}$$

Squaring shows that every component of Ψ satisfies the Klein–Gordon equation, so the vector branch is algebraically consistent. Its structure differs from the Dirac branches: the right multiplier is a spacelike vector, not a fixed even spacelike bivector, and therefore does not itself supply the usual Dirac complex phase.

Even/Odd Decomposition. Substituting the doublet decomposition into (9) and using $\gamma_0 s = -s\gamma_0$ gives

$$\nabla\psi_1 = -\mu\psi_1 s, \quad \nabla\psi_2 = +\mu\psi_2 s. \quad (10)$$

Thus ψ_1 and ψ_2 satisfy similar first-order equations with opposite signs. It is therefore sufficient to analyse

$$\nabla\psi = -\mu\psi s, \quad s^2 = -1. \quad (11)$$

Real Exponential Modes. For a real exponential ansatz $\psi(x) = Me^{k \cdot x}$ with constant even multivector M , substitution into (11) gives

$$kM = -\mu Ms.$$

Acting on this equation once more with k from the left and substituting back yields

$$k^2 M = -\mu k M s = \mu^2 M s^2 = -\mu^2 M.$$

For nonzero M the scalar $k^2 + \mu^2$ must therefore vanish, so

$$k^2 = -\mu^2.$$

Every nonzero real exponential mode thus has a spacelike wave vector. The real exponential ansatz produces only spacelike growth or decay modes, and oscillatory massive plane waves are not captured by a single real exponential.² Oscillatory solutions instead require the coupled real Clifford representation exhibited below.

Timelike Oscillatory Modes. Let p be a constant timelike mass-shell vector with $p^2 = \mu^2$, and set $\theta = p \cdot x$. For any constant even multivector amplitude M , viewed at this stage as an algebraic amplitude, the field

$$\psi(x) = M \cos \theta - \frac{p}{\mu} M s \sin \theta \quad (12)$$

is an oscillatory solution of (11). Since left multiplication by the vector p and right multiplication by the vector s change parity twice, the second term is again even when M is even. Indeed, since $\nabla\theta = p$,

$$\nabla\psi = -pM \sin \theta - \mu Ms \cos \theta,$$

while

$$-\mu\psi s = -\mu Ms \cos \theta - pM \sin \theta,$$

using $s^2 = -1$, so $\nabla\psi = -\mu\psi s$ as required. The special case $M = 1$ gives

$$\psi(x) = \cos \theta - \frac{p}{\mu} s \sin \theta.$$

²The same conclusion may be seen from the polar decomposition of a non-null even amplitude $M = \sqrt{\rho} e^{I\beta/2} R$. The equation $kM = -\mu Ms$ gives $k = -\mu e^{I\beta/2} s' e^{-I\beta/2}$ with $s' = R s \tilde{R}$. Since I anticommutes with vectors, $e^{I\beta/2} s' e^{-I\beta/2} = s' \cos \beta - s' I \sin \beta$, which contains both vector and trivector parts unless $\sin \beta = 0$. Since k is required to be a vector, one must have $\sin \beta = 0$, giving $k = \mp \mu s'$ with s' spacelike, in agreement with the scalar argument above.

The phase of these solutions is governed by the timelike wave vector p with $p^2 = \mu^2$, so the vector branch admits genuine Klein–Gordon mass-shell oscillatory modes. For fixed p and s , the two-sided operation

$$J_{p,s}(M) = \frac{p}{\mu}Ms$$

satisfies

$$J_{p,s}^2(M) = \frac{p^2}{\mu^2}Ms^2 = -M,$$

and therefore defines a real complex structure on the even amplitude space associated with that fixed mass-shell momentum.

However, $J_{p,s}$ is not a universal internal complex structure on the full field space. Different momentum sectors carry different operators $J_{p,s}$, since p enters the definition of the effective imaginary structure. A generic wave packet therefore does not share one universal local right-acting phase generator. By linearity, superpositions of mass-shell modes are again solutions of the first-order equation; the point is not the absence of wave packets, but the absence of a single momentum-independent internal phase generator shared by all momentum components.

A particularly transparent special case arises when $p = \mu u$ with $u^2 = 1$ and $u \cdot s = 0$, so that us is a simple bivector. In the rest frame $u = \gamma_0$ with $s = \gamma_3$ and $M = 1$, the solution becomes

$$\psi(t) = \cos(\mu t) + \sigma_3 \sin(\mu t), \quad \sigma_3 = \gamma_3 \gamma_0 = -\gamma_0 \gamma_3.$$

The oscillation moves between the scalar component and the bivector component σ_3 , making the Clifford-geometric character of the vector-branch oscillation explicit.

Physical Status. The vector branch is a genuine first-order root of the Klein–Gordon operator admitting massive timelike oscillatory modes. This establishes the existence of mass-shell solutions of the first-order root equation, but does not by itself supply positivity, a standard probability current, spin- $\frac{1}{2}$ representation content, or the fixed spin-plane complex structure of the Dirac equation.

Its oscillatory structure is generated by the two-sided momentum-dependent map $M \mapsto (p/\mu)Ms$ on each fixed mass-shell amplitude sector, rather than by a fixed right-acting even bivector phase. The vector branch does not therefore provide a universal local internal complex structure on the full field space, and is a non-Dirac massive first-order root structure within the present ansatz. Thus its status in the present paper is structural rather than phenomenological: it is classified as a homogeneous first-order root, not proposed here as a complete single-particle wave equation. Its conserved currents, possible Lagrangian formulation, and physical interpretation lie beyond the present classification.

The Trivector Branch

For the timelike trivector branch K is odd. In the adapted frame

$$K = \gamma_0 B, \quad B^2 = -1, \quad [B, \gamma_0] = 0,$$

where B is a simple spacelike bivector and γ_0 is orthogonal to the spacelike two-plane of B . The Dirac right multiplier K is odd, while the associated complex phase generator B is even; the significance of this distinction is taken up in the Remarks.

Since the polar decomposition (3) already contains an arbitrary Lorentz rotor, we may work in the canonical adapted representative

$$B = I\sigma_3, \quad K = \gamma_0 I\sigma_3.$$

The root equation then becomes

$$\nabla\Psi = -\mu\Psi\gamma_0 I\sigma_3, \quad \mu = \pm m. \quad (13)$$

This is the spacetime-algebra form of the Dirac equation. Since $K = \gamma_0 I\sigma_3$ is odd, the even and odd parts of Ψ decouple. Thus ψ_1 and ψ_2 each satisfy a separate Hestenes–Dirac equation, with the even bivector $I\sigma_3$ supplying the geometric complex structure. The trivector branch is therefore already in Dirac form, with a fixed right-acting even bivector phase generator.

The Spacelike Bivector Branch

The nontrivial even homogeneous root, apart from the pseudoscalar, is a simple spacelike bivector. As established above, we work in the adapted frame with

$$K = B, \quad B^2 = -1, \quad [B, \gamma_0] = 0.$$

For even K , the root equation produces a coupled system for the doublet:

$$\nabla\psi_1 = -\mu\psi_2\gamma_0 B, \quad (\nabla\psi_2)\gamma_0 = -\mu\psi_1 B, \quad \psi_{1,2} \in \text{Cl}^+(1, 3). \quad (14)$$

Since B commutes with γ_0 , multiplying the second equation on the right by γ_0 yields

$$\nabla\psi_2 = -\mu\psi_1 B\gamma_0 = -\mu\psi_1\gamma_0 B.$$

Defining the diagonal combinations

$$\psi_{\pm} := \psi_1 \pm \psi_2$$

and using (14), one finds

$$\nabla\psi_{\pm} = \mp\mu\psi_{\pm}\gamma_0 B.$$

Thus the diagonal combinations satisfy Dirac equations with odd right multipliers $\gamma_0 B$:

$$\nabla\psi_{\pm} = \mp\mu\psi_{\pm}\gamma_0 B, \quad (\gamma_0 B)^2 = -1. \quad (15)$$

Here B is the fixed even spacelike bivector supplying the geometric complex structure, and $\gamma_0 B$ is the odd Dirac right multiplier.

Internal Doublet Structure. In the original basis (ψ_1, ψ_2) , the equations (14) show a symmetric coupling between the two doublet entries. The diagonal combinations

$$\psi_{\pm} = \psi_1 \pm \psi_2$$

diagonalise this coupling and are themselves Dirac spinors. Thus the spacelike bivector root exposes an intrinsic two-dimensional internal space of Dirac modes: the pair (ψ_1, ψ_2) forms a Clifford doublet whose Dirac eigenmodes are ψ_{\pm} .

The bivector branch is Dirac-type, but in a different basis from the trivector branch. The trivector branch is already diagonal in the even/odd doublet decomposition; the bivector branch is off-diagonal in that basis and becomes Dirac only after the internal diagonalisation above.

The Pseudoscalar Branch

The second even choice with $K^2 = -1$ is the pseudoscalar:

$$K = I, \quad I^2 = -1, \quad I\gamma_0 = -\gamma_0 I.$$

Inserting this into the root equation, separating even and odd parts of $\Psi = \psi_1 + \psi_2\gamma_0$, and using $I\gamma_0 = -\gamma_0 I$, one obtains the coupled system

$$\nabla\psi_1 = -\mu\psi_2\gamma_0 I, \quad \nabla\psi_2 = +\mu\psi_1\gamma_0 I, \quad \psi_{1,2} \in \text{Cl}^+(1, 3). \quad (16)$$

This differs from the spacelike bivector case by a relative sign in the second equation.

To exhibit the equivalence with the vector-root type, choose an auxiliary spacelike bivector $B = I\sigma_3$ in an adapted frame and define

$$\psi_{\pm} := \psi_1 \pm \psi_2 I\sigma_3.$$

The auxiliary bivector is introduced only to diagonalise the two real components. It is not selected by the pseudoscalar root itself. Therefore the recombination does not reveal an intrinsic Dirac spin-plane; it only displays the reduction to vector-root equations.

Using (16),

$$\begin{aligned} \nabla\psi_{\pm} &= -\mu\psi_2\gamma_0 I \pm \mu\psi_1\gamma_0 I I\sigma_3 \\ &= -\mu\psi_2\gamma_0 I \mp \mu\psi_1\gamma_0\sigma_3 \\ &= \mp\mu(\psi_1 \pm \psi_2 I\sigma_3)\gamma_0\sigma_3 \\ &= \pm\mu\psi_{\pm}\gamma_3, \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

where in the last step we used

$$\gamma_0\sigma_3 = -\gamma_3.$$

Equivalently, this may be written as a vector-branch equation with spacelike right multiplier $-\gamma_3$:

$$\nabla\psi_{\pm} = \mp\mu\psi_{\pm}(-\gamma_3).$$

The pseudoscalar root therefore belongs to the non-Dirac vector-root sector rather than to the Dirac-type branches. Like the vector branch, it does not select a fixed right-acting even bivector phase generator as part of the root structure itself.

Remarks

Odd–Even Pairing of the Branches. The four homogeneous branches organise into two odd–even pairs. In the Dirac-type sector, the timelike trivector root is odd and already separates the even and odd parts of Ψ , while the spacelike bivector root is even and couples the two doublet entries before diagonalisation. In the vector-root sector, the same pattern occurs: the spacelike vector root is odd and separates the doublet components, while the pseudoscalar root is even and couples them before reducing, after internal recombination, to vector-root equations.

Thus the distinction between Dirac-type and vector-root-type propagation is independent of whether the root is odd or even. Each sector contains one already-separated representative and one doublet-coupled representative. The decisive distinction is whether the resulting propagation structure is governed by a fixed right-acting even bivector phase.

Dirac-Type and Vector-Root-Type Branches. All four primitive homogeneous branches are algebraically consistent first-order roots of the Klein–Gordon operator, but they are not equivalent as Clifford-geometric propagation structures.

The timelike trivector and spacelike bivector branches are the Dirac-type branches. Both reduce to Dirac equations for even Clifford spinors, though in different bases of the Clifford doublet. The trivector branch is already diagonal in the even–odd decomposition, with odd right multiplier $K = \gamma_0 B$. The bivector branch has even right multiplier $K = B$, couples the two doublet components, and becomes Dirac after the diagonalisation

$$\psi_{\pm} = \psi_1 \pm \psi_2.$$

In both cases the resulting Dirac equations are governed by a fixed right-acting even spacelike bivector

$$B^2 = -1,$$

which supplies the geometric complex structure.

The spacelike vector and pseudoscalar branches belong to the vector-root type. They admit massive Klein–Gordon mass-shell oscillatory modes, but their oscillatory structure is not generated by a fixed right-acting even bivector phase. In the vector branch the effective imaginary structure for a fixed mass-shell momentum sector is the two-sided operation

$$J_{p,s}(M) = \frac{p}{\mu} Ms.$$

For each fixed p , this defines a real complex structure on the corresponding amplitude sector. But different momentum sectors carry different operators $J_{p,s}$, so a generic wave packet does not share one universal local right-acting phase generator.

Thus the usual Dirac-type first-order structure is recovered only after one restricts to branches governed by a fixed right-acting even bivector phase. The full homogeneous Clifford classification is larger and also contains the non-Dirac vector-root sector.

Emergence of the Complex Structure. The Dirac-type branches select a spacelike bivector B with

$$B^2 = -1$$

as the geometric phase generator. In the canonical adapted frame this is

$$B = I\sigma_3.$$

Right multiplication by B generates the internal phase transformation

$$\Psi \mapsto \Psi e^{\alpha B},$$

providing the usual complex phase within the real spacetime algebra $\text{Cl}(1, 3)$. The complex structure of the Dirac branches therefore arises from a geometric element selected by the root structure itself, rather than from an externally postulated scalar imaginary unit.

The even bivector B supplies the phase generator, while the standard Hestenes–Dirac right multiplier is the odd element $\gamma_0 B$. In the trivector branch this odd multiplier appears directly as the root

$$K = \gamma_0 B.$$

In the bivector branch the root is the even element B , and the odd Dirac multiplier $\gamma_0 B$ appears only after diagonalising the doublet components.

Field Space of the Root Problem. The classification also clarifies why the real spacetime algebra is the natural intrinsic field space for the full homogeneous root problem. The right-acting element K is not known in advance; it is one of the structures to be classified. Prematurely replacing this right action by a fixed scalar imaginary unit, or by a preselected right-acting bivector, restricts the problem before the classification has been performed.

The full homogeneous root problem requires simultaneous left Clifford differentiation and homogeneous right Clifford multiplication as internal operations. These operations close internally on

$$\Psi(x) \in \text{Cl}(1, 3).$$

Within this field space, the even–odd decomposition gives the Clifford doublet

$$\Psi = \psi_1 + \psi_2 \gamma_0, \quad \psi_{1,2} \in \text{Cl}^+(1, 3),$$

and the Dirac complex structure appears as a selected right-acting spacelike bivector in the Dirac-type branches. The one-sided complex spinor module is therefore a natural reduced description of the Dirac-type sector, not the natural starting domain for the full homogeneous Clifford root problem.

Conclusion

We have classified the primitive homogeneous Clifford roots of the Klein–Gordon operator acting on real multivector fields in $\text{Cl}(1, 3)$. The classification concerns definite-grade right multipliers K in the homogeneous ansatz

$$\nabla \Psi = -\mu \Psi K,$$

with the second-order equation required to reduce directly to the scalar Klein–Gordon equation for arbitrary multivector fields. It is therefore narrower than a classification of arbitrary first-order linear systems or mixed-grade square roots.

For the scalar-mass ansatz the root condition is

$$\mu = \pm m, \quad K^2 = -1.$$

For homogeneous definite-grade K , this gives four primitive branches:

Root K	Grade	Doublet behaviour	Sector
$s, s^2 = -1$	1	diagonal	vector-root type
$\gamma_0 B, B^2 = -1$	3	diagonal	Dirac-type
$B, B^2 = -1$	2	off-diagonal	Dirac-type
I	4	off-diagonal	vector-root type

Here s is a spacelike unit vector, B is a simple spacelike bivector, and $\gamma_0 B$ represents a timelike trivector in an adapted frame. In the bivector case, the condition $B^2 = -1$ forces $B \wedge B = 0$, so the bivector root is simple and spacelike.

After choosing a timelike unit vector γ_0 , the full multivector field decomposes into the Clifford doublet

$$\Psi = \psi_1 + \psi_2 \gamma_0, \quad \psi_{1,2} \in \text{Cl}^+(1, 3).$$

This doublet is the even–odd structure of a single real multivector field expressed relative to a spacetime split.

The timelike trivector and spacelike bivector branches are the Dirac-type branches. Both reduce to Dirac equations for even Clifford spinors, though in different bases of the doublet. In both cases the propagation is governed by a fixed right-acting even spacelike bivector

$$B^2 = -1.$$

The trivector branch is already in Dirac form, with odd right multiplier $\gamma_0 B$. The bivector branch has even right multiplier B , couples the two doublet components, and becomes Dirac after diagonalisation via

$$\psi_{\pm} = \psi_1 \pm \psi_2.$$

The spacelike vector branch is also algebraically consistent and admits massive Klein–Gordon mass-shell oscillatory modes. However, these modes are generated by coupled real Clifford components rather than by a fixed right-acting even bivector phase. For a mass-shell mode with four-momentum p , the effective imaginary structure is the two-sided momentum-dependent operation

$$J_{p,s}(M) = \frac{p}{\mu} M s,$$

which satisfies $J_{p,s}^2 = -1$ on the even amplitude space associated with that fixed momentum sector. It does not define a universal internal complex structure on the full field space. The pseudoscalar branch reduces, after the internal recombination

$$\psi_{\pm} = \psi_1 \pm \psi_2 I \sigma_3,$$

to this same vector-root type.

The Dirac-type roots therefore clarify the geometric origin of the complex structure in the Dirac equation. The fixed right-acting bivector B , realised in the canonical adapted frame as

$$B = I\sigma_3,$$

generates the internal phase transformation

$$\Psi \mapsto \Psi e^{\alpha B}.$$

Thus the usual complex phase arises within the real spacetime algebra from the Dirac-type root structure itself. Within the present homogeneous Clifford classification, the usual Dirac-type first-order structure is the sector governed by a fixed right-acting even bivector phase, while the larger Clifford-algebraic root space also contains the non-Dirac vector-root sector.

A Pseudoscalar Left Mass Multiplier

In the main text we classified the scalar-mass roots

$$\nabla\Psi = -\mu\Psi K, \quad K^2 = -1.$$

For completeness we consider the Lorentz-covariant pseudoscalar-left alternative

$$\nabla\Psi = -\mu I\Psi K, \quad K^2 = -1. \tag{18}$$

The purpose of this appendix is not to define a second classification, but to show that the only other homogeneous left multiplier allowed by the lemma merely re-expresses the scalar-mass branches. The pseudoscalar-left ansatz introduces no new independent homogeneous root structure. It only rearranges the scalar-mass branches analysed in the main text.

Since I anticommutes with vectors in $\text{Cl}(1, 3)$,

$$\nabla(I\Psi K) = -I(\nabla\Psi)K.$$

Acting once more with ∇ on (18) gives

$$\nabla^2\Psi = -\mu\nabla(I\Psi K) = \mu I(\nabla\Psi)K = \mu I(-\mu I\Psi K)K = \mu^2\Psi K^2.$$

Matching the Klein–Gordon equation again requires

$$\mu = \pm m, \quad K^2 = -1.$$

Write

$$\Psi = \psi_1 + \psi_2\gamma_0, \quad \psi_{1,2} \in \text{Cl}^+(1, 3).$$

Since I commutes with even fields but anticommutes with γ_0 ,

$$I\Psi K = \psi_1 IK - \psi_2\gamma_0 IK.$$

Setting

$$L := IK,$$

the pseudoscalar-left equation becomes

$$\nabla\psi_1 + (\nabla\psi_2)\gamma_0 = -\mu\psi_1L + \mu\psi_2\gamma_0L. \quad (19)$$

Thus the pseudoscalar-left multiplier replaces K by its dual $L = IK$, together with a relative sign between the two doublet entries. The effective scalar-mass branch is determined only after this dualisation and the corresponding doublet reduction. In particular, the grade of K in the pseudoscalar-left equation is not, by itself, the grade of the effective scalar-mass right multiplier after doublet reduction.

Multiplication by I maps a spacelike vector to a timelike trivector and conversely, maps a spacelike bivector to its dual bivector, and maps the pseudoscalar I to the scalar -1 . We now examine the four homogeneous cases.

Spacelike vector $K = s$. Let

$$K = s, \quad s^2 = -1.$$

Then

$$L = Is, \quad L^2 = -1,$$

and L is a timelike trivector. Since L is odd, (19) decouples into

$$\nabla\psi_1 = -\mu\psi_1L, \quad (\nabla\psi_2)\gamma_0 = \mu\psi_2\gamma_0L.$$

After multiplying the second equation on the right by γ_0 , the two doublet entries satisfy scalar-mass trivector-root equations, up to the harmless sign choice already included in $\mu = \pm m$. This case therefore reduces to the Dirac-type trivector branch.

Timelike trivector $K = \gamma_0 B$. Let

$$K = \gamma_0 B, \quad B^2 = -1, \quad [B, \gamma_0] = 0.$$

Then

$$L = I\gamma_0 B.$$

In the canonical adapted frame $B = I\sigma_3$,

$$L = I\gamma_0 I\sigma_3 = \gamma_0\sigma_3 = -\gamma_3.$$

Thus L is a spacelike vector, up to sign. This case reduces to the scalar-mass vector branch.

Spacelike bivector $K = B$. Let

$$K = B, \quad B^2 = -1, \quad [B, \gamma_0] = 0.$$

Then $L = IB$. Since I commutes with bivectors,

$$L^2 = I^2 B^2 = +1.$$

Since B commutes with γ_0 while I anticommutes with γ_0 , the dual $L = IB$ anticommutes with γ_0 :

$$\gamma_0 L = -L \gamma_0.$$

Equation (19) then gives

$$\nabla \psi_1 = \mu \psi_2 \gamma_0 L, \quad \nabla \psi_2 = \mu \psi_1 \gamma_0 L.$$

With $\psi_{\pm} = \psi_1 \pm \psi_2$, one obtains

$$\nabla \psi_{\pm} = \pm \mu \psi_{\pm} \gamma_0 L.$$

The effective right multiplier is $\gamma_0 L$, not L itself. Using $\gamma_0 L = -L \gamma_0$, its square is

$$(\gamma_0 L)^2 = \gamma_0 L \gamma_0 L = -\gamma_0^2 L^2 = -(+1)(+1) = -1,$$

where we used $\gamma_0^2 = +1$ and $L^2 = +1$. In the canonical representative $B = I\sigma_3$,

$$L = IB = II\sigma_3 = -\sigma_3, \quad \gamma_0 L = -\gamma_0 \sigma_3 = \gamma_3.$$

Thus the effective right multiplier is a spacelike vector, and this case reduces to the scalar-mass vector branch. The apparent change of type is due to the dualisation $L = IK$ and the subsequent doublet reduction.

Pseudoscalar $K = I$. Let

$$K = I.$$

Then

$$L = I^2 = -1.$$

Equation (19) gives

$$\nabla \psi_1 = -\mu \psi_2 \gamma_0, \quad \nabla \psi_2 = \mu \psi_1 \gamma_0.$$

Choose an auxiliary spacelike bivector B with

$$B^2 = -1, \quad [B, \gamma_0] = 0,$$

and define

$$\psi_{\pm} = \psi_1 \pm \psi_2 B.$$

A direct substitution gives

$$\nabla \psi_{\pm} = \pm \mu \psi_{\pm} \gamma_0 B. \tag{20}$$

Thus this case reduces to Dirac equations with odd right multipliers $\gamma_0 B$, and hence to the scalar-mass bivector/Dirac branch.

Summary. The pseudoscalar-left ansatz permutes the homogeneous scalar-mass branches rather than producing new root structures. The effective branch is determined only after the dualisation $L = IK$ and the corresponding doublet reduction. The third row in the table below is the only potentially surprising one: although K is a bivector, the doublet reduction converts the effective right multiplier to the spacelike vector $\gamma_0 IB$.

K in $\nabla\Psi = -\mu I\Psi K$	Equivalent scalar-mass branch
spacelike vector	trivector/Dirac branch
timelike trivector	vector branch
spacelike bivector	vector branch
pseudoscalar I	bivector/Dirac branch

This table should not be read as a grade-duality table alone. In the pseudoscalar-left ansatz, the effective scalar-mass branch is determined by the right multiplier that appears after the doublet reduction, not by the original grade of K alone. Thus allowing a Lorentz-covariant pseudoscalar left multiplier introduces no new homogeneous branch beyond the scalar-mass branches classified in the main text.

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